

Likely Impacts of AI / AGI on the Modern Academic Journal Publication System

Rupert Macey-Dare¹ Updated 13 November 2025²

Compliance Statement

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Abstract

This paper considers the fundamental question of how robust or vulnerable to change is the modern academic journal publication system? To analyse this we consider the schematic diagrammatic model of the current system from a previous paper³, shown below, and then ask how each component block and set of interaction flows and relationships between blocks, is likely to be affected by developing AI and the path to AGI.

¹ Dr Rupert Macey-Dare LLM, see: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/cf_dev/AbsByAuth.cfm?per_id=732884 and <https://www.linkedin.com/in/rupertmacedare/>. Draft paper subject to correction, review and revision. All comments and communication on this and other matters and cases gratefully received.

N.B. This paper is independent academic research and comment of the author and does not constitute and should not be read as specific advice. Any calculations and examples are indicative and illustrative only.

***** 100% AI-free paper ***, *** Single author, no RA work *****

***** No external funding, funders or influencers*****

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² Original draft 12 November 2025

³ See: Macey-Dare Rupert: "Modern Academic Publication System- A Bitcoin-Mining Model" Zenodo 2025 at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17534894>

The conclusion from this thought experiment analysis is that every block in the current schematic production system for academic journal publication is likely individually to come under fundamental stress and change pressure from the advent and development of AI. The expected overall medium term outcome is that the commercial academic journal publication sector will shrink and become much less profitable. Meanwhile the production and flow rate of new academic research produced partly or totally using AI systems is likely to rise and that this will need to be published on other typically free to view platforms perhaps paid for by bundled advertising, rather like YouTube today.

Additionally the prominent, perhaps pre-eminent role today of academic journal publishing for academic credentializing, and the creation of valuable intangible publication assets for academic authors is likely to change, as knowledge dissemination becomes easier and cheaper and knowledge evaluation and objective independent calibration becomes easier and more effective, without the need for academic journal credit scoring and cross-branding. All together this suggests that AI may help bring about the end of a golden age of high profitability and growth for academic journal publishing, with an upcoming period of lower profitability and industry retrenchment, and a fundamental adjustment to the way academic publishing and knowledge creation is used by both academics and universities.

Seasoned academics with long established academic journal publication records are likely to be temporarily but ultimately unsuccessfully resistant to this coming seismic change.

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A Current Baseline Simple Illustrative Model

The diagram above shows a simple model of an academic ecosystem where academic publications are produced, are valued and valuable and help drive different flows around the model.

The model includes different schematic blocks of different actors, connected by arrows representing different directed flows of assets or money in a graph, flowing between different blocks.

Occasionally arrows between blocks are 2 way. There can be a number of arrows between pairs of blocks and each block is typically connected by arrows to one or more blocks.

Ultimately there are directed paths along the arrows that connect almost all the blocks together and a general circular flow between all the blocks. This represents a relatively stable setup where flows of assets and money circle round the system over different time periods, such as an academic year and periods of years and

Model Diagram Main Component Blocks- Key

- 1. Typical Academic Co-Author Team
- 2. Theoretical + Conceptual Universe (available to study)
- 3. Empirical + Data Universe (available to study)
- 4. Academic Publishers
- 4a. Academic Publisher Staff + Shareholders
- 5. Other Services (provided by external providers to publishers)
- 6. Reviewers/ Referees
- 7. Other Academic Teams (of different co-authors)
- 8. General Public + Other Readers (of academic journal publications)
- 9. Academic Libraries
- 10. Students (typically at universities)
- 11. University

- 12. Academic Funders
- 13 Government

Model Diagram Types of Flow- Key

The main flows connecting blocks in the diagrammatic model are as follows:

Key to diagram flows

Note that the flows in the pink block above are all of notional intangible assets. What this paper will argue is that the academic formal publication process is akin to the mining of crypto-currency like Bitcoin, which can in turn be converted/ transmuted into standard currency flows such as \$ or £ in the pockets of academic authors/ co-authors, and this circular payment mechanism helps to rationalize and explain the

current academic publication system including a number of peculiar and at 1st glance counter-intuitive aspects.⁴

The full model is illustrated in the Diagram above, but we now discuss the key component blocks and their main linkages to other blocks. N.B. This model is highly stylized and so needs to be changed mutatis mutandis for the real world. However the intention and objective to help explore and articulate major features and drivers of the prevailing current system.

Note on Diagrammatic Analysis Above

The diagrammatic analysis of the proposed system combines elements from all of the following:

- Network diagrams
- Stock flow diagrams
- Production diagrams
- Decision making diagrams
- Knowledge production diagrams

This is because the proposed system includes all these elements (and additionally random network links, and reduplication and generalization, not illustrated for clarity)

⁴ This analysis applies to representative average, median academic teams and academic work production. It does not apply to world leading, top end, say Nobel Prize or Fields Medal quality research, which by definition have multiple non-representative features including exceptional quality and rarity.

This analysis also does not apply to the academic monograph books, although there will be some applicability, mutatis mutandis, to book edited collections of papers from multiple co-authors with supervising author editors.

Likely Impacts of AI Systems on Individual Blocks this System Components + Overall System Model

1...Likely Impacts of AI on Block 1. Typical Academic Co-Author Team

Typical academic co-author teams are likely to use AI systems and tools as standard and to use AI systems as effective co-authors, whether expressly or implicitly credited or not. Some or all co-author team members may be replaced by AI, so it should become relatively common for an academic co-author team to include 1 author and 1 or more AI systems, or indeed for the team to be just 1 or more AI systems, possibly with additional human co-authors in extra research assistant or human fixer roles.

Author team analysis of and experimentation on and simulation of the Block 2. Theoretical + Conceptual Universe (available to study) and Block 3. Empirical + Data Universe (available to study) is likely to be carried out using and by AI systems linked with the co-author team, perhaps exclusively.

Interactions with other blocks in the model including Block 7. Other Academic Teams (of different co-authors) is also likely to involve or be delegated to AI systems on each side, leading to AI algorithmic interaction and game playing cooperation, collusion, competition etc.

The shadow cost of research and paper production is likely to fall with the advent of AI systems, increasing the natural production rate of academic papers *ceteris paribus*. This will lead to increased demand from publication teams for publication platforms but probably with less money to pay for publication and so an increasing switch to free working paper platforms.

7...Likely Impacts of AI on Block 7. Other Academic Teams (of different co-authors)

This is likely to be exactly the same as for Block 1, assuming that these academic teams are all typical draws from the whole academic team pool.

2..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 2. Theoretical + Conceptual Universe (available to study)

The advent of AI will expand the tools and approaches available to study the Theoretical and Conceptual Universe area. AI and the theory of AI will also become a greater component part of this area and so a field of conceptual study itself. AI will also both augment and substitute out of human investigation of this area.

3..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 3. Empirical + Data Universe (available to study)

The advent of AI will also expand the tools and approaches available to study the Empirical and Data Universe area. AI and AI use and data simulation and modelling will also become a greater component part of this area and so a field of conceptual study itself. AI will also both augment and substitute out of human investigation of this area.

4..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 4. Academic Publishers

Academic publishers will be impacted by AI in multiple ways. Firstly they are likely to use AI to augment or replace staff and other systems and reduce costs. Secondly they are likely to switch some or all publication from human author groups to humans plus AI or AI only. Thirdly they are likely to try to exploit the special value of their publications for training AI systems.

Additionally the number of publishing academics is likely to fall and the amount of monopoly rent academic publishers can extract through traditional subscription academic journals is also likely to fall possibly dramatically. This means that there is likely to be some switching of academic publication from these journals to pre-paid

open access journals and to free working papers. If produced by traditional academic publishers these might be supported by additional advertising, similar to YouTube.

However one cannot avoid the conclusion that the returns to academic publishers are likely to fall dramatically and so the number of large academic publisher groups is likely to fall and consolidate in a declining industry.

4a..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 4a. Academic Publisher Staff + Shareholders

AI is likely to be used to replace academic publisher staff, perhaps to almost none and to increase operational efficiency. Thus other factors equal, AI is likely to reduce publisher costs and increase profitability. However other factors will probably not be equal and income from academic journal publication is also likely to fall dramatically. Which of these countervailing forces will dominate and how quickly is unclear.

5..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 5. Other Services (provided by external providers to publishers)

The uptake of AI by external service providers will tend to both reduce costs and extend the range of other services that can be provided to publishers. It may also make it easier for more other services to be absorbed and bundled in with their key product by academic publishers.

6. Likely Impacts of AI on Block 6. Reviewers/ Referees

There is already strong anecdotal feedback from the academic publishing community of AI chatbot systems being used to write what are purportedly human reviewer comments, and to advise on and effectively make reviewer decisions, often hilariously badly.

In future, improving AI systems are likely to augment and in some cases completely replace human review system. This could also provide administrative and logistical benefits to Block 4 academic publishers.

It would also provide a benefit to Block 6 Reviews and Referees in that they would have to do less real work in this area, perhaps none. But there would be the corresponding disbenefit of reduced or no reviewer / referee publicity credits and internal reward.

This last aspect might however be replaced / replicated by journal article editors being replaced by a human supervisory oversight board.

8..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 8. General Public + Other Academic Journal Readers

The general public and other readers of academic journal publications are likely to be strong adopters and users of AI systems and to use them both to search for knowledge and to summarize it from web sources and even to outsource some or all of their thinking and analysis. This in turn is likely to reduce demand from this group for academic journal publications and to reduce total resources available to pay for academic journal publications and so to reduce the number of academic journal that can be sustained on a pay per view basis by this group towards zero.

9..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 9. Academic Libraries

Academic Libraries will increasingly use AI systems for research and knowledge retrieval. Library resources may also be replaced partly or fully by AI systems. Students may substitute into AI systems directly rather than using library services. Non AI library services may also shrink in response to funding pressure and reduced funding from universities and students. This in turn will reduce Library resources for funding of paid journal access, which may in turn increase demand for pay to publish academic journals and free access working papers.

10..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 10. Students (typically at universities)

Firstly student demand for universities is likely to fall as they become able to replicate most of the teaching and learning and even outsource the thinking and decision making to A.I. systems. Arguably this was already a long term trend with the globalization of good low cost information such as Wikipedia and the advent of low cost often financially free university level courses online e.g. university MOOCs and the telecoms and smartphone and computing revolutions that allow very low cost search for and transmission of information across the globe.

If the relative value and demand for university education falls with the evolution of AI, then universities will need some combination of shrinkage and sectoral consolidation, and reduction in pricing and improvement in quality *ceteris paribus*. Overall this is likely to decrease the real value of university income from students and so decrease the amounts payable for academic journals.

Students are already using AI systems to help with all aspects of their university work, including project design ,essay design and drafting and full essay writing. Universities can respond by some combination of a blind eye, banning or restricting AI systems, embracing AI systems and changing their student evaluation systems both in terms of how performance is measured, e.g. using a return to pen + paper exam scripts in timed invigilated human exams and changing what is actually learned and tested.

Taken together this is likely to reduce funding for university students and probably also student numbers and/or costs per course and so reduce one of the fundamental inflows of money into the current academic publishing system.

[11..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 11. University](#)

There are likely to be multiple impacts of AI on universities. Firstly AI is likely to be used to increase operational efficiency and substitute out staff and certain types of research. Secondly AI is likely to be used to help select and determine what academics to employ, what academic projects to pursue, what resources such as libraries and their paid journal subscriptions to invest in and how to deliver education. The advent of AI is also likely to reduce student demand and funding and

government demand and funding and hence university resources. This shock is likely to lead to major contraction in the university sector both in terms of number and size of universities and number of academics employed. Publication pressure on academics is likely to increase, with focus either on a reduced number of top subscription journals or on open access free journals.

12..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 12. Academic Funders

Academic Funders are likely to use AI to streamline their operations and logistics and replace staff. Projects to fund may be chosen either partly or fully by and using AI systems. In turn the projects that are funded may be more or even fully AI implemented. This could in turn reduce the number and size of funding grants made available to human researcher and human author teams. It may be that academic funders just absorb academic research and produce their own AI dominant or totally AI produced academic research, in which case they would probably want to take over the whole knowledge publication and dissemination process as well.

The advent of AI is also likely to challenge the whole current university model, with reduced demand from students and reduced income and reduced perceived relevance for universities for education and technological progress. The advent of online MOOCs has in recent years confirmed that the marginal cost of delivering the same courses as last year is approximately zero, without an academic's salary. So universities faced with cost pressures are likely to reduce staff and academic numbers and replace them with online resources and AI systems. Thus the number of academics trying to produce academic journal publications is likely to fall, while the ratio of trained academics competing for remaining academic positions is likely to rise. This is likely to produce increased publication pressure on existing employed and challenger academics but with less financial resources. A prediction therefore would be that average academic publication quality will fall, but production rate will rise possibly switching into free journals and working papers.

13..Likely Impacts of AI on Block 13 Government

National and Local Government will be hugely affected by AI developments in multiple ways. Firstly they are likely to use AI systems to try to improve their own productivity and reduce costs. So their own decisions about university and project funding may become partly or fully AI based. Secondly their demand for university research may fall as AI appears to have more of the answers. Thirdly if there is net displacement of the labour force by AI, then other demands for government funding will increase, while tax based inflow of funds will decrease. Taken together this is likely to reduce National and Local Government funding for and support for universities and university projects and so reduce one of the fundamental inflows of money into the current system.

Conclusion

The conclusion from this thought experiment analysis is that every block in the current schematic production system for academic journal publication is likely individually to come under fundamental stress and change pressure from the advent and development of AI. The expected overall medium term outcome is that the commercial academic journal publication sector will shrink and become much less profitable. Meanwhile the production and flow rate of new academic research produced partly or totally using AI systems is likely to rise and that this will need to be published on other typically free to view platforms perhaps paid for by bundled advertising, rather like YouTube today.

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References (to be expanded)

Macey-Dare, Rupert, How Soon is Now? Predicting the Expected Arrival Date of AGI- Artificial General Intelligence (June 30, 2023). Available at SSRN:

<https://ssrn.com/abstract=4496418>

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